

Surface Basicity, Base Strength and Catalytic Activity of Some Mixed Oxides Containing TiO_2

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The number and the strength of basic sites on the surfaces of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2$, $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$ and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-TiO}_2$ heat-treated at various temperatures were determined by acid adsorption method using various acids in the range of $\text{pK}_a = 0.64$ to 9.9 . It is observed that $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$ and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2$ have strong basic sites with base strength at $\text{pK}_a = 9.9$, while $\text{SiO}_2\text{-TiO}_2$ has weaker basic sites with base strength at $\text{pK}_a = 0.64$ to 4.41 . The basicity at various base strengths and also surface area decreases with increasing temperature of heat-treatment.

A study of the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide by these catalysts indicates that basic centres which are strong as well as those which are moderately weak ($\text{pK}_a \geq 10$) are able to catalyse the decomposition of H_2O_2 . It is further observed that the catalytic activity of these mixed oxides decreases in the same order as the basicity.

A NUMBER of methods for determining acidity and acid strength of solid surfaces have been reported and extensively used for the study concerning the correlation between catalytic activity and acidic property of solid catalyst¹⁻³. Very little work, however, has been done on basic property of solid surfaces. Some of the methods used so far are (i) to observe the colour change of bromothymol blue adsorbed on the solid surface when suspended in benzene,⁴ (ii) to measure the amount of phenyl vapour adsorbed on the solid⁵, and (iii) the exchange method.⁶ As these methods have not given very satisfactory results, the present work is initiated to study the basicity and base strength distribution of some mixed oxides by the acid adsorption technique using various acids in the range of $\text{pK}_a = 0.64$ to 9.9 . In order to test how the catalytic activity correlates with the base strength of the catalyst, the decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in presence of these catalysts has been studied.

Experimental

Merck's quality H_2O_2 which was purified by distillation at reduced pressure was used in this investigation. All other chemicals used in this work were AnalaR quality chemicals. The mixed oxides were prepared by the precipitation and coprecipitation technique as described earlier.¹⁻²

Measurement of surface area and basic property :

The surface area of mixed oxide heat-treated at various temperatures was determined by the liquid adsorption method using ethylene glycol monoethyl ether.⁷

The basicity of mixed oxide catalyst was measured by back titrating the excess of the trichloroacetic acid.⁸ For this purpose, 0.5 g of the catalyst was suspended in 50 ml solution of $0.025M$ trichloroacetic acid in dry benzene and the mixture was agitated for 2 hrs. The mixture was kept aside for 24 hrs. The suspension was filtered off and 5 ml of the solution was titrated against $0.02M$ *n*-butylamine in dry benzene using bromothymol blue as indicator. The basicity of the mixed oxide surface was calculated from the decrease in trichloroacetic acid concentration in benzene. Similarly the base strength of mixed oxide was determined by acid adsorption method using comparatively weaker acids such as chloroacetic acid ($\text{pK}_a = 2.66$), acetic acid ($\text{pK}_a = 4.41$) and phenol ($\text{pK}_a = 9.9$) and these values are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Measurement of catalytic activity :

The decomposition of H_2O_2 reaction was selected for the study of the catalytic activity of the catalysts. For this purpose 100 ml. of $0.2M$ solution of H_2O_2 in double distilled water and 1.0 g of mixed oxide catalyst were kept in a flask maintained at 30° in a thermostat. The H_2O_2 underwent decomposition in the presence of the basic centres and was estimated by titrating the undecomposed H_2O_2 against $0.01M$ KMnO_4 solution at regular intervals of time. Experiments were carried out with samples of the catalyst that had been ignited for 6 hrs at different temperatures in the range 100° to 1000° .

Since the present catalysts have both acidic as well as basic centres on their surfaces and that both these sites catalyse the decomposition of H_2O_2 , an attempt has been made to evaluate the amount of decomposition brought about by basic sites by

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TABLE 1 BASICITY, BASE STRENGTH DISTRIBUTION AND CATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$ (68%-32%) CATALYST.

Temp. of heat treatment °C	Surface area m^2/g	Basicity, m.moles/g, calculated from the absorption of acids				Decomposition of H_2O_2 $k \times 10^2 \text{ hr}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$
		pKa = 0.64	pKa = 2.66	pKa = 4.41	pKa = 9.9	
120	128.1	1.40	1.015	0.762	0.60	16.0
210	82.7	1.12	0.946	0.682	0.50	13.6
360	62.7	0.96	0.648	0.584	0.26	6.9
440	59.3	0.62	0.542	0.432	0.19	5.1
520	49.6	0.48	0.436	0.346	0.15	4.6
600	47.9	0.36	0.302	0.264	0.11	3.0
700	38.7	0.24	0.201	0.168	—	—
800	32.7	0.16	0.122	0.104	—	—
1000	8.0	0.09	0.085	0.056	—	—

TABLE 2 BASICITY, BASE STRENGTH DISTRIBUTION AND CATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2$ (73%-26%) CATALYST.

Temp. of heat treatment °C	Surface area m^2/g	Basicity, m.moles/g, calculated from the absorption of acids				Decomposition of H_2O_2 $k \times 10^2 \text{ hr}^{-1} \text{g}^{-1}$
		pKa = 0.64	pKa = 2.66	pKa = 4.41	pKa = 9.9	
120	283.8	1.30	0.92	0.65	0.18	4.58
210	267.8	1.16	0.86	0.62	0.16	4.16
320	265.0	0.88	0.66	0.50	0.15	3.86
420	208.6	0.75	0.60	0.44	0.13	3.22
500	197.1	0.70	0.54	0.40	0.13	3.16
600	152.1	0.60	0.50	0.35	0.11	2.86
700	147.9	0.44	0.36	0.30	—	—
800	113.9	0.30	0.24	0.18	—	—
1050	21.8	0.18	0.16	0.11	—	—

poisoning⁹ the acidic sites with neutral red (pKa = 6.8). Since the decomposition of H_2O_2 is a very sensitive reaction¹⁰, the catalyst samples used were those which had the same basic properties before the start of every decomposition reaction.

Results and Discussion

It is seen from the values presented in Tables 1 and 2 that the basicity and base strength distribution changes remarkably with the rise in temperature of heat treatment. In Fig. 1 is given the plot of base strength in pKa values of acids used for adsorption studies against the total basicity (mmoles/g) for $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2$ catalyst calcined at various temperatures. Similar curves were obtained for $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$ and $\text{SiO}_2\text{-TiO}_2$ catalysts. This plot is similar to the one obtained for acid strength distribution of some mixed oxides.¹¹ The base strength of the surface increases as the pKa value of acid increases. It is observed in case of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2$ (Table 1, Fig. 1), and $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2$ (Table 2) the basicity and base strength stronger than pKa = 9.9 appear on the surface when heat treated at 120° to 600° and those at medium base strength pKa = 2.66~4.41 appear on the surface at 120° to 1000°. In case of $\text{SiO}_2\text{-TiO}_2$ (Fig. 2), it has no strong basic centres at pKa = 9.9 but has number of weak basic centres at pKa = 2.66~4.41. It is observed that the basicities and base strengths decrease in the following order: $\text{TiO}_2\text{-ZrO}_2 > \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2 > \text{SiO}_2\text{-TiO}_2$.

Fig. 1. Basicity, base strength of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-TiO}_2$ catalyst calcined at various temperatures.

The values obtained by the phenol adsorption are generally lower than the values obtained by the adsorption of other acids. This probably is because, the other acids are strong (pKa = 0.64~4.4), and are

able to measure even weak basic sites whereas phenol is a weaker acid ($pK_a = 9.9$) and measures only strong basic sites. The phenol adsorption method does not show any basic sites at some of the elevated temperatures of calcination of the mixed oxides (above 600°) in all cases as strong basic centres are absent and only weak basic centres are present on the surface.

Fig. 2. Basicity vs. Temperature of heat treatment.

Fig. 3. Basicity vs. Temperature of heat treatment.

In Fig. 3 is plotted the basicity values (mmoles/g) at various base strengths against the temperature of calcination for TiO_2-ZrO_2 catalyst. A similar plot was obtained for $Al_2O_3-TiO_2$ catalyst. It is observed from Figs. 2 and 3 that the basicity at various base

strengths decreases with the temperature of heat treatment. It has been observed earlier that the acidity of mixed oxides attains a maximum and then decreases with the rise in temperature of heat treatment.¹¹ It has been explained that acid sites are created due to loss of water. Since basicity only decreases as observed by us, it can be explained and represented in the same manner as has been done by Hindin and Weller¹² in case of alumina, i.e., the two basic sites present on the surface which were due to the OH groups, of the surface have now been converted into an acid site and a basic site. This procedure continues till all the OH groups of the surface are eliminated as water and the acidity value attains a maxima. With further rise in temperature, there are no OH groups to be lost as water molecules, and structural changes take place on the surface which reduce the surface area, which is evident from the values of surface area presented in Tables 1 and 2 and this accounts for reduction in surface basicity.

The values of the first order rate constant k of the mixed oxides heat treated at various temperatures for decomposition of H_2O_2 reaction are given in the last columns of Tables 1 and 2. It is observed that the basicity values measured by phenol adsorption correlate well with catalytic activity. Both phenol and H_2O_2 have a pK_a value in the range¹³ 9 to 11. Since the pK_a values of phenol and H_2O_2 are nearly the same, the basicity values measured by phenol adsorption are catalytically active in the decomposition of H_2O_2 . The basicity values measured by other strong acids ($pK_a = 0.64 \sim 4.41$) are high and do not correlate with the catalytic activity, as these acids measure even very weak basic sites which are not able to catalyse the decomposition of H_2O_2 . In case of TiO_2-ZrO_2 (Table 1) and $Al_2O_3-TiO_2$ (Table 2) samples heat treated at 120° to 600° have strong basic sites at $pK_a = 9.9$ and are catalytically active. In case of TiO_2-ZrO_2 and $Al_2O_3-TiO_2$ samples heat treated at 700° , 800° and 1000° have no basic sites at $pK_a = 9.9$ but have a number of basic sites at $pK_a = 0.64$ to 4.41 and these relatively weak basic sites are considered to be catalytically inactive. A similar observation was made in case of SiO_2-TiO_2 catalyst. As the pK_a value of H_2O_2 is about 10, it needs basic sites either equal to or stronger than this for the H_2O_2 decomposition. Neutral red ($pK_a = 6.8$) is unable to catalyse the decomposition of H_2O_2 and this supports our view expressed above and our earlier observation.⁹

It is further observed from the results of Tables 1 and 2 that the catalytic activity of these mixed oxides decrease in the same order as the basicity. Naruko⁶ observed a parallel relation between the basicity and the catalytic activity of nitrous oxide activated charcoal for the decomposition of H_2O_2 .

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